

Molecular interaction studies on metal chlorides in aqueous saccharide solvent mixtures at 303.15 K

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Abstract : Ultrasonic velocity (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) have been measured for calcium chloride (CaCl_2), cadmium chloride (CdCl_2) and magnesium chloride (MgCl_2) in water and water-lactose mixture of different concentrations (0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 mol dm^{-3}) at 303.15 K. The measured data have been used to evaluate various acoustic parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K), apparent molal volume (ϕ_V), limiting apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K^0), limiting apparent molal volume (ϕ_V^0) and their constants (S_K , S_V), transfer partial molal volume ($\Delta\phi_V^0$), viscosity A- and B-coefficient of Jones-Dole equation and transfer B-coefficient (ΔB). The results have been discussed in terms of solute-co-solute and ion-solvent interactions present in the systems.

Keywords : Adiabatic compressibility, apparent molal compressibility, apparent molal volume, transfer partial molal volume, transfer B-coefficient.

Introduction

In the present work, density (ρ), ultrasonic velocity (U) and viscosity (η) of CaCl_2 , CdCl_2 and MgCl_2 in water and aqueous lactose mixtures at 303.15 K were determined experimentally. The measured data have been used to derive desired parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K), apparent molal volume (ϕ_V), limiting apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K^0), limiting apparent molal volume (ϕ_V^0) and their constants (S_K , S_V), transfer partial molar volume ($\Delta\phi_V^0$), viscosity A- and B-coefficient of Jones-Dole equation and transfer B-coefficient (ΔB). These derived parameters shed more light on solute-co-solute and ion-solvent interactions among the systems studied.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in this present research work are spectroscopic reagent (SR) and analytical reagent (AR) grades of minimum assay of 99.9% obtained from E. Merck, Germany and Sd Fine chemicals, India, which are used as such without further purification. Water used

in these experiments was deionized, distilled and degassed prior to prepare solutions. Required amount of water and lactose were taken to prepare the composition of binary mixtures (0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.2 mol dm^{-3}) in a clean dry conical flask with a ground stopper. The required quantity of metal chlorides for given molarity was dissolved in binary mixture of aqueous lactose and similar procedure has been adopted for different molarities of metal chlorides. For each concentration, the mass of the metal chloride can be measured using electronic digital balance having an accuracy of ± 0.1 mg (Model : Shimadzu AX-200). The density was determined using a specific gravity bottle by relative measurement method with an accuracy of ± 0.1 kg m^{-3} . An Ostwald's viscometer (10 ml capacity) was used for the viscosity measurement and efflux time was determined using a digital chronometer within ± 0.01 s. An ultrasonic interferometer having the frequency 3 MHz (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, Model : F81) with an overall accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$ has been used for velocity measurement. An electronically digital operated constant temperature bath (RAAGA Industries) has

been used to circulate water through the double walled measuring cell made up of steel containing the experimental solution at the desired temperature. The accuracy in the temperature measurement is ± 0.1 K.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of density (ρ), ultrasonic velocity (U) and viscosity (η) of the three metal chlorides namely calcium chloride (CaCl_2), cadmium chloride (CdCl_2) and magnesium chloride (MgCl_2) in water and aqueous lactose mixtures at 303.15 K are presented in Table 1. The values of adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K), apparent molal volume (ϕ_V), limiting apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K^0), limiting apparent molal volume (ϕ_V^0), and their constants (S_K , S_V), transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_V^0$), viscosity A- and B-coefficient of Jones-Dole equation and transfer B-coefficient (ΔB) are given in Tables 2 and 3.

In all the three metal chloride systems studied, the values of density (Table 1) and ultrasonic velocity are found to increase with increase in concentration of metal chloride as well as aqueous lactose. Molecular interaction is thus responsible for the observed increase in velocity in these mixtures. The factors apparently responsible for such behaviour may be due to the presence of interactions caused by the ion transfer reactions of metal chloride in aqueous lactose mixtures. The increase in ultrasonic velocity in these solutions may be attributed to the cohesion brought about by the ionic hydration. Further, it is observed the magnitude of ultrasonic velocity is smaller in MgCl_2 which shows that it possesses strong molecular interaction.

From Table 2, it is observed that the values of adiabatic compressibility decreases with increase in concentration of aqueous lactose mixture as well as metal chlorides. The decrease in adiabatic compressibility can be attributed to two effects¹: (i) decrease in compressibility caused by the introduction of incompressible ions; and (ii) the change of solvent structure around the ion.

The contribution of the effect (i) is generally larger and depends more on concentration than on the kind of ions. The addition of electrolyte lowers the compressibility of the solvent due to orientation of the solvent molecules around the ions which normally increases the inter-

nal pressure. The adiabatic compressibility values are found to be greater in MgCl_2 than the other two metal chlorides, showing a strong ionic interaction.

Further, it is observed from the above table, (i) The values of ϕ_K and ϕ_V are negative over the entire range of molarity. (ii) The values of ϕ_K and ϕ_V increases with increasing the concentration of metal chlorides and aqueous lactose mixtures. (iii) The magnitude of ϕ_K is in the order: $\text{MgCl}_2 > \text{CaCl}_2 > \text{CdCl}_2$.

The negative values of ϕ_K and ϕ_V indicates ionic and hydrophilic interactions occurring in these systems². The observed behaviour of ϕ_K and ϕ_V reveals that strengthening of the ion-solvent interaction in all the systems studied. The magnitude of ϕ_K which strongly supports our earlier view of the ultrasonic velocity and adiabatic compressibility. Further, the negative values of ϕ_V indicates electrostrictive solvation of ions³.

The limiting apparent molal compressibility ϕ_K^0 provides information regarding ion-solvent interaction and S_K that of ion-ion interaction in the solutions. From Table 3, it is observed that ϕ_K^0 values are negative and increases with increasing the concentration of aqueous lactose mixtures in all the systems studied. The appreciable negative values of ϕ_K^0 shows the existence of ion-solvent interactions. Further it can be noted that the magnitude of ϕ_K^0 is in the order: $\text{MgCl}_2 > \text{CaCl}_2 > \text{CdCl}_2$. Values of S_K exhibits positive in all the three systems, suggesting the presence of weak ion-ion interaction in the mixtures.

The volume behaviour of a solute at infinite dilution is satisfactorily represented by ϕ_V^0 , which is independent of the ion-ion interactions and provides information concerning ion-solvent interactions. Table 3 reveals that the values of ϕ_V^0 are negative and follows the same trend as that of ϕ_K^0 in all system studied which further confirms the presence of strong ion-solvent interaction. The negative S_V values suggest the presence of weak ion-ion interactions⁴ and thus complex ion formation taking place in the systems.

The possible type of interactions occurring between the metal chlorides and aqueous lactose mixtures can be classified as follows:

(i) Ionic-hydrophilic interactions between the ions of metal chlorides (Ca^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Cl^-) and polar group of saccharide (-OH sites) and (ii) ionic-hydropho-

Table 1. Values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of metal chlorides in aqueous lactose mixtures at 303.15 K

Molarity M (mol dm^{-3})	ρ (kg m^{-3})				η ($\times 10^{-3} \text{ Nsm}^{-2}$)				U (m s^{-1})						
	Water + lactose				Water + lactose				Water + lactose						
	0.00 M	0.05 M	0.10 M	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.00 M	0.05 M	0.10 M	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.00 M	0.05 M	0.10 M	0.15 M	0.20 M
	System-I : Water + lactose + calcium chloride														
0.00	995.7	1003.3	1012.2	1021.7	1030.1	0.7977	0.8381	0.8631	0.8817	0.9201	1518.0	1525.8	1531.6	1540.8	1542.2
0.20	1014.4	1024.0	1028.7	1032.7	1039.6	0.8474	0.9054	0.9390	0.9652	0.9935	1561.2	1591.2	1597.8	1601.4	1605.6
0.40	1030.4	1051.9	1056.4	1059.6	1067.9	0.8876	0.9765	1.0085	1.0307	1.0589	1570.2	1595.4	1602.6	1606.8	1610.0
0.60	1047.6	1079.0	1083.5	1087.6	1094.7	0.9303	1.0501	1.0840	1.1102	1.1422	1577.4	1601.4	1609.2	1612.8	1616.4
0.80	1062.8	1089.2	1094.2	1098.8	1106.4	0.9762	1.0877	1.1209	1.1465	1.1796	1584.0	1604.4	1611.6	1615.2	1618.8
1.00	1080.3	1099.8	1107.1	1112.5	1119.6	1.0394	1.1305	1.1668	1.2087	1.2541	1593.0	1607.2	1615.2	1619.0	1623.0
	System-II : Water + lactose + cadmium chloride														
0.00	995.7	1003.3	1012.2	1021.7	1030.1	0.7977	0.8381	0.8631	0.8817	0.9201	1518.0	1525.8	1531.6	1540.8	1542.2
0.20	1029.6	1034.5	1042.0	1050.6	1056.1	0.8491	0.8813	0.9049	0.9219	0.9607	1608.0	1598.4	1572.0	1560.0	1549.2
0.40	1060.8	1065.4	1071.7	1080.4	1087.0	0.8912	0.9298	0.9540	0.9708	1.0106	1626.2	1618.8	1589.4	1578.6	1565.4
0.60	1089.0	1091.6	1101.8	1107.1	1108.9	0.9431	0.9666	0.9884	1.0084	1.0450	1647.0	1641.0	1615.8	1603.2	1590.0
0.80	1114.8	1121.7	1131.5	1137.3	1144.2	0.9835	1.0208	1.0464	1.0657	1.1108	1673.4	1666.8	1638.6	1622.8	1612.8
1.00	1146.6	1150.1	1160.6	1165.0	1175.3	1.0328	1.0694	1.0928	1.1154	1.1622	1700.2	1692.6	1667.4	1650.0	1633.2
	System-III : Water + lactose + magnesium chloride														
0.00	995.7	1003.3	1012.2	1021.7	1030.1	0.7977	0.8381	0.8631	0.8817	0.9201	1518.0	1525.8	1531.6	1540.8	1542.2
0.20	1016.0	1023.6	1026.1	1034.4	1042.5	0.8574	0.9122	0.9604	0.9969	1.0485	1544.4	1546.9	1563.0	1568.4	1570.4
0.40	1030.7	1035.3	1038.4	1046.7	1054.2	0.9098	0.9578	1.0065	1.0641	1.1165	1553.4	1561.2	1565.4	1570.8	1574.4
0.60	1042.2	1043.6	1054.0	1058.2	1064.5	0.9723	1.0262	1.0783	1.1319	1.2037	1556.4	1565.4	1568.4	1573.2	1578.0
0.80	1053.7	1056.3	1063.8	1069.6	1076.0	1.0355	1.0989	1.1533	1.2018	1.2702	1561.8	1570.4	1575.0	1580.4	1586.4
1.00	1067.4	1089.2	1094.6	1102.2	1111.0	1.0992	1.2141	1.2524	1.3023	1.3702	1572.0	1578.6	1583.4	1590.6	1592.6

Note

Table 2. Values of adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K) and apparent molal volume (ϕ_V) of metal chlorides in aqueous lactose mixtures at 303.15 K

Molarity M (mol dm^{-3})	β ($\times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ N}^{-1}$)					$-\phi_K$ ($\times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ N}^{-1}$)					$-\phi_V$ ($\times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)				
	Water + lactose					Water + lactose					Water + lactose				
	0.00 M	0.05 M	0.10 M	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.00 M	0.05 M	0.10 M	0.15 M	0.20 M	0.00 M	0.05 M	0.10 M	0.15 M	0.20 M
0.00	4.3584	4.2813	4.2116	4.1227	4.0817	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.20	4.0446	3.8570	3.8077	3.7759	3.7313	2.9783	2.5632	2.3628	1.9559	1.9402	102.43	100.60	79.09	51.98	44.21
0.40	3.9363	3.7350	3.6857	3.6554	3.6126	2.4350	1.8842	1.7745	1.5506	1.5472	84.41	114.99	103.20	87.38	85.77
0.60	3.8364	3.6139	3.5641	3.5348	3.4963	2.2486	1.6507	1.5736	1.4230	1.4023	82.79	116.41	108.22	98.71	95.34
0.80	3.7501	3.5667	3.5188	3.4884	3.4491	2.1275	1.3514	1.2925	1.1818	1.1687	79.12	98.12	92.41	85.71	83.55
1.00	3.6477	3.5200	3.4623	3.4293	3.3908	2.0810	1.1731	1.1442	1.0598	1.0455	78.51	87.32	84.55	79.75	77.47
System-II : Water + lactose + cadmium chloride															
0.00	4.3584	4.2813	4.2116	4.1227	4.0817	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.20	3.7563	3.7835	3.8835	3.9112	3.9453	3.7524	3.1547	2.2605	1.6406	1.1971	165.14	150.11	141.08	134.43	119.31
0.40	3.5647	3.5818	3.6937	3.7143	3.7542	2.6966	2.4112	1.9137	1.6132	1.3821	153.89	145.05	136.94	132.76	126.86
0.60	3.3852	3.4019	3.4763	3.5143	3.5671	2.3027	2.0937	1.8469	1.5883	1.3781	143.22	134.19	133.72	125.65	114.79
0.80	3.2033	3.2089	3.2915	3.3388	3.3600	2.0955	1.9720	1.7706	1.5630	1.3673	133.94	131.33	130.03	124.18	120.83
1.00	3.0171	3.0350	3.0991	3.1529	3.1899	2.0018	1.8727	1.7300	1.5480	1.3631	132.00	127.05	126.15	120.22	119.76
System-III : Water + lactose + magnesium chloride															
0.00	4.3584	4.2813	4.2116	4.1227	4.0817	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.20	4.1265	4.0827	3.9893	3.9300	3.8896	1.6038	1.4261	1.4007	1.2197	1.2062	100.13	98.64	66.72	59.89	57.54
0.40	4.0207	3.9629	3.9299	3.8720	3.8269	1.2273	1.1374	0.9768	0.8789	0.8757	85.06	76.82	62.12	58.25	55.29
0.60	3.9610	3.9103	3.8570	3.8183	3.7726	1.0016	0.9049	0.8809	0.7528	0.7423	74.49	63.95	65.10	56.07	52.09
0.80	3.8907	3.8388	3.7895	3.7432	3.6929	0.9893	0.8358	0.7960	0.7160	0.7133	68.91	62.32	59.71	54.60	51.58
1.00	3.7911	3.6842	3.6439	3.5861	3.5487	0.9785	0.9637	0.9106	0.8614	0.8536	67.23	78.42	64.19	51.30	50.51

Table 3. Values of limiting apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K^0), limiting apparent molal volume (ϕ_V^0), constants (S_K , S_V) transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_V^0$), viscosity A- and B-coefficient of Jones-Dole equation and transfer B-coefficient (ΔB) of metal chlorides in aqueous lactose mixtures at 303.15 K

Metal chlorides	Water + lactose	M (mol dm ⁻³)	$-\phi_K^0$ ($\times 10^{-7}$ m ² N ⁻¹)	$-\phi_V^0$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ m ³ mol ⁻¹)	S_K ($\times 10^{-7}$ N ⁻¹ m ⁻¹)	$-S_V$ (mol ^{-3/2})	$\Delta\phi_V^0$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$-A$ ($\times 10^{-2}$ dm ^{-3/2} mol ⁻¹)	B ($\times 10^{-2}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	ΔB ($\times 10^{-2}$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹)
CaCl ₂	0.00	3.5825	102.12	1.5947	24.90	-	0.21	27.67	-	
	0.05	3.5695	93.18	2.4609	26.26	8.94	5.77	30.96	3.30	
	0.10	3.2540	88.79	2.1667	6.28	13.33	8.27	28.43	0.76	
	0.15	2.6288	45.69	1.5934	46.70	56.43	8.91	28.67	1.00	
	0.20	2.6190	36.05	1.5982	54.98	66.07	3.49	32.87	5.20	
	0.00	4.9047	193.22	3.1143	63.46	-	1.84	27.42	-	
CdCl ₂	0.05	4.0071	170.39	2.2757	43.80	22.83	1.29	28.55	1.13	
	0.10	2.5902	153.52	0.9148	26.58	39.70	1.79	28.15	0.73	
	0.15	1.7195	147.45	0.1719	26.68	45.77	2.90	29.10	1.68	
	0.20	1.0241	122.91	0.4725	3.46	70.31	3.54	29.37	1.95	
	0.00	1.7704	125.16	0.4439	61.35	-	1.28	30.61	-	
	0.05	1.7669	110.12	0.9515	45.47	15.04	2.86	44.08	13.47	
MgCl ₂	0.10	1.6795	60.24	0.9156	7.10	64.92	6.28	36.00	5.39	
	0.15	1.4170	51.41	0.7086	11.48	73.75	13.44	31.92	1.31	
	0.20	1.3017	47.48	0.6798	13.23	77.68	15.54	31.71	1.10	

Note

bic interactions between the ions of metal chlorides and the non-polar side group of saccharide

The $\Delta\phi_v^0$ value, by definition, is free from solute-solute interactions and therefore provides information regarding solute-solvent interactions⁵. The values of $\Delta\phi_v^0$ (Table 3) are positive and it increases with increasing the molarity of lactose mixture. The higher magnitude of $\Delta\phi_v^0$ observed for $MgCl_2$ than for $CdCl_2$ and $CaCl_2$ reflects the stronger and more extensive interaction between metal chloride and lactose. The $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values can also be explained on the basis of co-sphere overlap model⁶ in terms of solute-co-solute interactions. According to this model, ionic-hydrophilic group interactions contribute positively whereas ionic-hydrophobic group interactions contribute negatively to the $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values. Therefore, from Table 3, the positive $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values observed for all the three metal chlorides suggest that the former types of interactions are dominating over the later

Viscosity is another important parameter in understanding the structure as well as molecular interactions occurring in the solutions. From the Table 1 it is observed that the values of viscosity increases with increasing concentration of metal chlorides as well as aqueous lactose mixtures. This increasing trend indicates the existence of molecular interaction occurring in these systems. In order to shed more light on this, the role of viscosity B-coefficient has been obtained from Jones-Dole equation⁷. A perusal of Table 3 shows that the values of the A-coefficient are negative and B-coefficient is positive. Since A is a measure of ionic interaction, it is evident that there is a weak ion-ion interaction in the mixtures studied, which is indicated by the negative and smaller magnitude of A values⁸. The viscosity B-coefficient⁹ reflects the effect of ion-solvent interactions on the solution

viscosity. The positive B values suggest the presence of strong ion-solvent interaction. The magnitude of B is in the order $MgCl_2 > CaCl_2 > CdCl_2$. The larger value of B shows structure making capacity of the solute. Further, the ΔB values shown in Table 3 which supports the result obtained from $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values discussed above.

Conclusion

In summary, from the magnitudes of β , ϕ_K^0 and viscosity B-coefficient, it can be concluded that $MgCl_2$ in aqueous lactose solution possess the strong ion-solvent interaction than the other two metal chlorides. The transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_v^0$) and transfer B-coefficient (ΔB) suggests the predominance of ion-hydrophilic group interactions over the ion-hydrophobic interactions. From the co-sphere overlap model it can be concluded that solute-co-solute interactions are dominating over the ion-solvent interactions.

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